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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Analyzes growing rejection of performativity in DEI initiatives, with employees demanding authentic structural changes. Discusses psychological consequences of tokenism and empty promises on mental health of queer and racialized professionals. Offers organizational strategies to implement genuine equity through transparency, shared decision-making power, and affirmative policies that systematically address workplace inequalities.

Keywords

social justice, stigma, social determinants

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